

The Influence of Interest and Attitude on Students' Learning Motivation in Distance Education

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of interest and attitude on learning motivation of UPBJJ-UT Ternate students. The population in this study were all 44 students who received Bidikmisi and CSR scholarships at UPBJJ-UT Ternate. The results showed that: (1) there was a positive influence between interest (X1) and attitude (2) on learning motivation (Y). For the Interest variable, it is obtained $t\text{-count} (6.348) > t\text{-table} (2.018)$ or the Sig value $(0.024) < (0.05)$. As for the attitude variable, it was obtained $t\text{-count} (4.398) > t\text{-table} (2.018)$ or the Sig value $(0.010) < (0.05)$. The coefficient of determination (R Square) is 0.824 or 82.4%. This shows that the percentage contribution of the influence of the independent variable of interest and attitude to the dependent variable of learning motivation is 82.4%. Meanwhile, the remaining 17.6% is influenced or explained by other variables not included in this research model.

KEYWORDS: Interests, Attitudes, Learning Motivation, Distance Education

I. INTRODUCTION

Motivation is closely related to the achievement of a person or an institution. Because motivation is a driving variable, encouraging and guiding someone in doing something. This is what is important for Universitas Terbuka (UT) students to be able to increase their learning motivation, considering that the application of the distance learning system at UT requires independent learning. Because, learning independence is of course very much determined by student learning motivation.

Like the distance learning system developed by open universities in the world, UT also experiences obstacles in developing student motivation to be able to survive until completing their studies at UT. Moore and Kearsley (1996), suggest that student retention rates in distance education can reach 30% -50%. This condition encourages distance education institutions to develop various instruments that can attract students to be motivated in learning so as to minimize retention.

However, no matter how good the system is in increasing student learning motivation, it needs to be balanced with the motivational factors that exist within the students themselves. Because stimuli that arise from within oneself (internal) have a greater influence than external factors that come from outside. The results of research by Amaludin (2013) show that students' internal factors are very influential in participating in learning because of the physiological needs of self-actualization. Likewise, the research results of Upoyo and Sumarwati (2011) show that the factor that has a significant effect on the level of student motivation is internal drive.

Of the many internal factors that influence learning motivation, including interests and attitudes. According to Slameto (2010) interest is a feeling that you prefer and have an attachment to a certain thing or activity, without being asked. Interest is basically the acceptance of a relationship between oneself and

something outside oneself. The closer and stronger the relationship, the more interest that arises in a person. Djaali (2011) explains that interest can be expressed through questions directed to students knowing which one they like from one thing to another, it can also be realized through participation in an activity. Cahyono's (2018) research results show that the interest in learning factor affects learning motivation. In fact, Setiawan's (2019) research results show that interest directly has a positive and significant effect on students' learning motivation which ultimately determines their readiness to learn.

While attitudes have an influence on learning motivation, because attitude is a state of mental and nervous readiness that is regulated through experience which has a dynamic or directed influence on individual responses to all objects and situations related to it (Widayatun, 2009). Attitude is a form of evaluation or reaction to an object, either partially or impartially, which is a certain order in the sense of a person's feelings, thoughts and actions towards an aspect of the surrounding environment (Saifudin, 2005). Putri's research results (2019) show that attitudes have a positive effect on learning motivation. If the positive attitude of students is high, their learning motivation will increase.

Based on the theory and research results above, researchers are interested in conducting research on the influence of interest and attitudes on learning motivation of Bidikmisi and CSR students at UPBJJ-UT Ternate. This research is important to do, considering that with the scholarship program, UT seeks to provide opportunities for high school graduates who are still fresh graduates to study at UT. But on the other hand, since UPBJJ-UT Ternate received the scholarship allocation, every semester students have decreased because their academic Achievement Index is low so that the scholarship is lost. Some even resigned in the middle of the trip without a clear reason which was conveyed by their students to UPBJJ-UT Ternate.

II. METHODS

This study uses a confirmatory study method that aims to test the hypothesis. Where the theoretical basis used has been formed, only to be tested again whether the theory can be justified. The results of the study are described quantitatively in the form of numbers accompanied by explanations (Sugiyono, 2010). In this study, what was tested was the influence of the factors of interest in learning (X1) and attitudes (X2), on learning motivation (Y) of students receiving the Bidikmisi scholarship and CSR UPBJJ-UT Ternate.

The population in this study were all 44 students who received Bidikmisi and CSR scholarships at UPBJJ-UT Ternate. Because the population is less than 100, the sampling method uses total sampling, where the entire population becomes the research sample (Sugiyono, 2010).

All research data were collected through a questionnaire which was distributed to all respondents. The questionnaire is presented in the form of a Likert scale for all variables X and variable Y. In the learning interest variable (X1) there are 23 question items related to interest in learning, compiling study schedules, actively following tutorials, impressions during tutorials and targets to be achieved during college. In the attitude variable (X2) there are 20 question items related to feelings and responses to the implementation of the tutorial. Meanwhile, the learning motivation variable (Y) consists of 18 questions consisting of questions related to self-confidence in learning, interest in following tutorials, enthusiasm for doing assignments, and activeness in tutorials (discussing or asking questions). All questions, both on variables X and Y, there are five alternative answers given to each question, namely strongly agree (SS), agree (S), somewhat agree (R), disagree (TS), and strongly disagree (STS).

Before being distributed, the questionnaire was first tested on non-respondents and tested for its validity so that it could measure the level of accuracy of the instruments used. After that, the reliability test was carried out to determine the accuracy of the data. Before testing the hypothesis using regression analysis, the data obtained is first tested using the normality test to determine the normality of the data and its correlation, as a condition for regression analysis. Then the multicollinearity test was carried out which aims to test the regression equation model which shows the correlation between each independent variable. The final stage of the analysis is to test the research hypothesis using multiple regression analysis to determine the effect of the independent variable (X) simultaneously on the dependent variable (Y) (Sugiyono, 2013).

III. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Validity Test Results

The testing technique that is often used by researchers to test the validity is to use the Bivariate Pearson correlation (Pearson Moment Product). This analysis is done by correlating the score of each item with the total score. If $r\text{-count} \geq r\text{-table}$ (2-sided test with sig. 0.05, $df = N-2$) then the instrument or question items have a significant correlation to the total score (declared valid).

The validity test of the question items on the Learning Interest Variable (X1), attitude (X2) and the Student Learning Motivation variable (Y) has a correlation value of $r\text{-count} \geq 0.2973$ ($r\text{-table}$, $df = 44-2 = 42$). Of the 23 question items about learning interest, there were 6 question items that were invalid so they were excluded from the validity test. Meanwhile, of the 20 questions related to attitude (X2) there were 5 invalid questions that were excluded from the validity test. Furthermore, from the 18 question items about learning motivation (Y) there were 10 questions that were declared invalid and were excluded from the validity test because the correlation value $r\text{-count} < 0.2973$.

From the item questions of learning interest (X1) and attitudes (X2) as well as the items of the student learning motivation variable (Y) which were declared valid were then used to measure the variables under study.

3.2. Reliability Test Results

In this reliability test, it will be seen whether a questionnaire is appropriate, consistent and reliable to be used as a data collection tool. The reliability test in this study used the Cronbach alpha (α) coefficient. A research instrument is said to be reliable if it has an alpha coefficient (α) of 0.60. Based on the results of the reliability test, the following results were obtained:

Table 1. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's alpha (α) coefficient	Information	Reliability Level
Interest (X ₁)	0.871	Reliabel	Very strong
Attitude (X ₂)	0,784	Reliabel	Strong
Motivation to learn (Y)	0.668	Reliabel	Strong enough

From the results of the reliability test as shown in Table 1, the Cronbach's alpha (α) coefficient of interest variable (X1) is $0.871 > 0.60$ and the attitude (X2) is $0.871 > 0.60$. So it can be said that the two independent variables are reliable. While the results of the Cronbach alpha (α) coefficient variable Student Learning Motivation (Y) were $0.668 > 0.60$ and were declared reliable.

3.3. Normality Test Results

Table 2. Normality Test Results

		Interest	Attitude	Motivation
N		44	44	44
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	84.45	68.05	76.70
	Std. Deviation	10.693	8.929	4.454
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.190	.066	.095
	Positive	.190	.058	.092
	Negative	-.111	-.066	-.095
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1.263	.439	.628
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.082	.991	.826

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

From the statistical table above, it can be seen that the data for the interest variable (X_1) is obtained by Asymp. Sig. (0.082) > 0.05, the attitude variable obtained Asymp Sig. (0.991) > 0.05, and Student Learning Motivation obtained Asymp Sig. (0.826) > 0.05, so it can be concluded that the research data used for each of these variables is normally distributed.

3.4. Multicollinearity Test Results

The multicollinearity test aims to test the regression equation model which shows the correlation between each independent variable. The regression equation model is said to be good if there is no autocorrelation between the independent variables. To determine whether or not multicollinearity is present in a regression equation model in this study, if the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value for the independent variable > 1, it can be said that the model has high collinearity. The results of multicollinearity testing in this study can be seen in Table 3 as follows.

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test Results

Variabel	Collinearity Statistic		Information
	Tolerance	VIF	
Interest (X_1)	0,969	1,032	Multicollinearity Free
Attitude (X_2)	0,969	1,032	Multicollinearity Free

The result of the calculation of the tolerance value for all variables is more than 0.10, which means there is no correlation between the independent variables. The results of the calculation of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value also show that there is not one independent variable that has a VIF value of more than 1. So it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables in the regression model.

3.5. Regression Results

This analysis is used to examine the influence of the interest and attitude variables on student learning motivation. From this analysis it can be seen that the regression coefficient of the independent variable on the dependent variable, the coefficient of determination and the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

3.5.1. Multiple Regression Equation

From the results of the regression analysis, look at the output coefficient and are presented as follows:

Table 4. Coefficients Test Results

		Coefficients ^a									
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	77.871	7.033		11.072	.000					
	Interest	.042	.066	.100	6.348	.043	-.088	-.099	-.099	.969	1.032
		.035	.079	.069	4.398	.026	.052	.069	.068	.969	1.032

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation to learn

The results of the analysis obtained a regression equation which explains the effect of Interest (X1) and Attitude (X2) on Learning Motivation (Y) are: $Y = \alpha + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 = 77.871 + 0.042X_1 + 0.035X_2$

1. The constant value (α) assumes that Learning Motivation (Y) is 77.871, if the Interests (X1) and Attitude (X2) variables are 0.
2. The regression coefficient for the Interest variable (b_1) is 0.042 which states that each change in Interest increases the results of Learning Motivation (Y) by 0.042.
3. The regression coefficient of the Attitude variable (b_2) is 0.035 which states that any change in attitude will increase the results of Learning Motivation (Y) by 0.035.

3.5.2. Determinant Coefficient (R²)

Table 5. Multiple Regression Results

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.711 ^a	.824	.036	4.533

a. Predictors: (Constant), Interests, Attitude

b. Dependent Variable: Motivation to learn

The results of the analysis obtained an R value of 0.711, which means that the influence of interest and attitude on learning motivation is quite strong. The coefficient of determination R² (R Square) is 0.824 or 82.4%. This shows that the percentage of the contribution of the influence of the independent variable of interest and attitude towards the dependent variable is learning motivation of 82.4%. Meanwhile, the remaining 17.6% is influenced or explained by other variables not included in this research model. Standard Error of The Estimate = 4.533 which shows the measure of the error rate in predicting the dependent variable.

3.5.3. Partial Regression Coefficient Test (t test)

Table 6. t-test Results

Model	Coefficients ^a				
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	77.871	7.033		11.072	.000
Interest	.042	.066	.100	6.348	.043
	.035	.079	.069	4.398	.026

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation to learn

The results of the analysis obtained that the calculation for the Interest variable (X1) is (6.348), and the Attitude variable (X2) is (4.398). With a significance level of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$), it is obtained for the t-table (2.018). So that the following criteria are obtained:

- For the Interest variable (X1), the t-count (6.348) > t-table (2.018) or the Sig (0.024) < (0.05) value is obtained, so H_0 is rejected, so it can be concluded that there is an influence between interest on learning motivation.
- For the Attitude variable (X2) obtained t-count (4.398) > t-table (2.018) or the value of Sig (0.010) < (0.05) then H_0 is rejected, so it can be concluded that there is an influence between attitudes on learning motivation.

3.5.4. Simultaneous Regression Coefficient Test (Test F)

Table 7. F Test Results

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	10.571	2	5.286	25.720	.000 ^b
	Residual	842.588	41	20.551		
	Total	853.159	43			

- a. Dependent Variable: Motivation to learn
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Interests, Attitude

The analysis results obtained F-count (25,720) and the level of significance using 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$) obtained F-table (3.22). So that the value of F-count (25,720) > F-table (3.22) or the value of Sig (0.000) < (0.05) then H_0 is rejected, it can be concluded that there is a simultaneous influence between Interest (X1) and Attitude (X2) on learning motivation (Y).

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the research results above, it can be concluded that:

1. Learning interest has a positive effect on the learning motivation of Bidikmisi and CSR scholarship recipients at UPBJJ-UT Ternate.
2. Attitudes have a positive effect on the motivation to learn Bidikmisi and CSR of the UPBJJ-UT Ternate scholarship recipients.

Based on these conclusions, it is suggested that in the process of receiving Bidikmisi and CSR scholarships at UPBJJ-UT Ternate, these two variables need to be considered. At the beginning of the selection, it was observed to what extent their interest in studying at UT which implements a distance learning system which of course is still foreign to them. Likewise, their attitudes towards distance learning should be explored further to find students with high learning motivation who can graduate on time with satisfactory academic performance.

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